

THE PROBLEM OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' ORAL SPEECH AND ITS SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: *In this thesis, the author reflects on the problem of developing students' oral speech and ways to solve it, as well as offers suggestions and recommendations for addressing this issue in the modern era of information technologies. These recommendations are based on the author's many years of experience and research conducted by international scholars in this field.*

Keywords: oral speech, student, modern problem, conservatory, language culture, text.

Introduction

Among the comprehensive reforms being carried out in the education system of New Uzbekistan, one of the crucial tasks in the higher education system is training qualified personnel, developing students as individuals, and nurturing them as necessary and mature members of society (DPN[№]-5847, 2019). The development of oral speech is a key component in this process and is of utmost importance.

Communication culture is one of the most important elements in nurturing intellectual specialists and individuals capable of a creative approach to education in

higher education. The correct formation of speech is systematically regulated at all stages of education.

Method

Speech is a form of emotional expression in communication and plays an important role in human life regarding its ability to influence others (Juslin P. & Laukka P., 2004). Developed speech is one important means of ensuring an individual's active participation in society (Bylkova S., 2021). Therefore, to develop students' speech, teachers choose educational methods based on proven traditions for correctly shaping their pronunciation, vocabulary, logical sentence structure, and syntactic construction (Rosado L. & Vaca-Cárdenas M., 2023).

In the modern world, against the backdrop of advancing technology, several problems are emerging, such as the underdevelopment of oral speech from young to old, especially students' inability to freely express their thoughts, and the prevalence of too many jargon and borrowed words in their speech (Kent R. D. , 2015).

Several main reasons can explain the emergence of these problems.

First, most assessments are conducted in multiple-choice format in general secondary education. Although this saves time, it leads to deficiencies in schoolchildren's speech.

Second, because young people often complete their homework and assignments on computers and mobile devices via the Internet, they need to engage with high-quality literature sufficiently. This leads to the underdevelopment of vocabulary, which is a key component of speech culture.

Third, reading mass media in electronic form, on websites or social media, is also one of the main factors hindering speech development. This is because the audience, who reads information on social networks and websites only in the form of headlines and leads, perceives the text in separate, disjointed parts, leading to the formation of fragmented speech.

All of the factors listed above result in students being unable to easily and freely express their opinions in a foreign language and their native language. Therefore, in-depth mastery of all aspects of the native language is considered important for developing speech culture among students, even those in non-philological fields.

Results and Discussion

Compared to students in social sciences and humanities, teachers face more challenges in developing the speech culture of non-philological students (Ishanova N.R., 2024). In the first stage of teaching speech culture to non-philological students, convincing them, they can speak their native language as fluently and eloquently as possible is crucial (Ilhamova I.N., 2022). This is a key component of the “Speech Culture” course, which is designed to instill confidence in students’ oral speech abilities. Teachers often encounter students’ fear of making mistakes, which negatively affects their speech. It is crucial to make every effort to address this problem early. Experience shows that after the first practical sessions of the “Speech Culture” course, students acquire correct sentence construction and pronunciation skills. In developing students’ speech, it is also appropriate to utilize their creative abilities, such as singing techniques (Deutsch D. & et. al., 2006). To achieve positive results, repeating this practice several times is recommended.

When students engage in free communication for the first time, it is important not to correct mistakes in their speech before they finish their sentences. This may lead to hesitation and fear in their subsequent speech. By listening to the students’ speech and working on their mistakes and shortcomings, they gradually develop the ability to overcome these feelings.

We can use various types of dialogue work to develop students’ oral speech. In the first stage of speech development, this may include the following types of tasks:

- Arranging the dialogue text in a logical sequence (you can further complicate this task by adding one or more additions or removing irrelevant comments);

- Replacing underlined expressions with synonymous phrases (for example, when studying greetings, politeness, and other forms of communication);
- Repeating missing comments indicated in the key in mini-dialogues (in subsequent stages, you can increase the number of comments or not provide the key so that students not only find suitable phrases but also create them themselves);
- Completing the dialogue if the conclusion lacks one or more final lines, and so on.

When developing speech culture in non-philological students, it is recommended to begin with a dialogical form of oral speech development, as it firstly simulates real-life communication in various situations, and secondly, it is easier than a monologue.

To develop oral expression skills on a given topic, you can use classic types of tasks: retelling the text, creating a story based on an image, continuing or concluding a given text, and so on.

In addition, tasks of particular interest, such as role-playing games based on popular television programs, positively influence the development of students' monologue speech. In completing this type of task, one of the students plays a leading role, while the others are invited guests, each of whom plays their role. As an example, we can consider a television talk show with the theme "The Role of Libraries in the Life of Modern Man" (participants: host; Director of the National Library named after A. Navoi; Head of the University Library; poets and writers; students and others).

This form of interactive learning fosters a culture of monologic speech among students and develops their ability to deliver presentations in front of an audience.

Conclusion

Thus, the tasks for developing oral monologue speech in non-philological students can be diverse. The key is not to overlook recognize the mistakes made by

young people, to provide timely warnings and corrections, and, of course, to vary the types of tasks. This is because different, innovative approaches in practical classes engage the audience and achieve effective results.

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TALABALARNING OG‘ZAKI NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MUAMMOSI VA ULARNING YECHIMLARI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tezisda muallif talabalarning og‘zaki nutqini rivojlantirish muammosi va ularning yechimlari xususida mulohaza yuritib, bugungi axborot texnologiyalar asrida ushbu masalaning yechimlari xususida o‘z taklif va tavsiyalarini beradi. Ushbu tavsiyalar muallifning ko‘p yillik tajribalari hamda jahon olimlarining bu borada olib borgan tadqiqotlariga tayanilgan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: og‘zaki nutq, talaba, zamonaviy muammo, konservatoriya, til madaniyati, matn.